

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Solar energy atlas with global maps of solar energy potential and variability therein
Deliverable number	D50 (Del. Rel. No. D9.5)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	18/07/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	WU
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

The report presents maps of mean global solar energy and of the temporal variability of global solar energy derived from the SR- ESM output and provided.

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WP9

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Executive summary

We developed a solar energy atlas based on the 30-year (2020 - 2049) km-scale global climate simulations produced with IFS and ICON. For both simulations, we show global maps of the mean solar photovoltaics (PV) potentials as well as the inter-annual variability and decadal trends thereof. IFS and ICON produce similar global patterns in annual mean PV potential, although PV potentials based on the ICON data are generally higher. Both simulations also show good agreement on the standard deviation of the annual-mean PV potential, with arid regions showing the strongest inter-annual variability, but mostly produce very different decadal trends. Furthermore, we identify ≥ 3 -day warm & dry spells to study the impact of extreme weather situations on PV energy production. We find that, except in arid climates, these warm & dry event mostly result in higher PV potentials compared to days not identified as a warm & dry spell. Last, we present a brief overview of the evaluation of the models in terms of their potential for estimating PV energy production, which has been performed by Iberdrola.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP9	Relevance in this deliverable?
Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics (O2)	no
Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs (O2)	no
Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution (O3)	yes

1 Introduction

The storm-resolving climate models developed within the nextGEMS project simulate the coupled global circulations of the atmosphere and oceans at kilometer-scale grid spacings. By better resolving local landscape features (e.g. orography) and small-scale processes (e.g. convection), and by allowing small-scale improvements to affect the global circulation, we expect a better representation of e.g. surface solar irradiance (see deliverable D9.3 for an evaluation thereof) compared to coarser global models or regional climate models that prescribe the large-scale flow. By producing realistic global climatological datasets at high spatiotemporal resolution, the goal is that these km-scale models are able to serve as accurate digital twins of the Earth system, for example to support policy, decision making, and planning regarding renewable energy production such as solar photovoltaics (PV).

In this report, we present a solar energy atlas (deliverable D9.5) produced with the high-resolution global nextGEMS datasets of surface solar irradiance and other near-surface meteorological variables. We focus on the mean photovoltaics (PV) potential as well as the trends and inter-annual variability therein. Furthermore, we consider the impact of warm and dry events on the potential PV energy production. Finally, we show some results from the evaluation of the models in terms of their potential for estimating PV energy yield, which has been performed by Ibedrola.

2 Methodology

2.1 Simulation data

We use the 30-year (2020-2049) km-scale global climate simulations produced with the IFS-FESOM (Rackow et al., 2025) and ICON-Sapphire (Hohenegger et al., 2023) models within cycle 4 of the nextGEMS project (Segura et al., 2025). IFS-FESOM (hereafter: IFS) is the Integrated Forecasting System version 48r1 (ECMWF, 2023), with modifications documented by (Rackow, Becker, et al., 2023), coupled to the Finite-Element/volumE Sea ice-Ocean Model v2.5 (Rackow, Hegewald, et al., 2023). ICON-Sapphire (hereafter: ICON) is the Sapphire configuration (Hohenegger et al., 2023) of the ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic model. The simulations have a horizontal resolution of about 9 (IFS) and 10 (ICON) kilometers in the atmosphere and about 5 kilometers in the ocean, but the data are available on an Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelisation (HEALPix; Górski et al., 2005) grid. We use the highest available zoom level, which corresponds to a horizontal resolution of about 12.7 km. We neglect the first simulation year (2020), because 2020 is not complete in IFS as the simulation starts at 20 January 2020. Both simulations follow the SSP3-7.0 scenario for greenhouse gas concentrations (O'Neill et al., 2016).

2.2 Photovoltaics potential

To estimate the potential solar photovoltaics (PV) energy production, we first compute hourly PV capacity factors. The PV capacity factor is defined as the ratio of the actual power production to the installed power production capacity and depends mostly on meteorological conditions. The annual mean capacity factor multiplied by the number of hours per year (365×24) then gives the annual potential energy production in KWh per installed kW peak (kWp). The computation of the PV capacity factors follows the approach of Jerez et al. (2015) and Feron et al. (2021), using the Cycle 4 ICON and IFS simulation data from 2021 to 2049. The ICON data is provided at 15 minute resolution and first averaged to hourly values, the IFS data is already provided at hourly resolution.

We assume PV panels are mounted flat on the ground, so that we do not have to account for tilt angle, panel orientation, or direct-diffuse partitioning. This assumption allows us to isolate the impact of meteorological conditions on the PV potential and trends thereof, but may result in significant biases at higher latitudes: compared to an optimal tilt angle, we likely underestimate the PV potential by about 50% in the mid-latitudes and over 100% at the poles Jacobson and Jadhav, 2018. However, we assume these biases are constant in time and similar in IFS and ICON

The PV capacity factor CF_{PV} is computed as:

$$CF_{PV} = (1 - S)\eta \frac{G}{G_{STC}}, \quad (1)$$

where G is the global horizontal irradiance and G_{STC} is the global horizontal irradiance at standard testing conditions (1000 W m^{-2}). S is the fraction of the global horizontal irradiance that is lost due to soiling, that is, dust accumulation on the PV panel. η is the relative PV panel efficiency given by

$$\eta = 1 + \beta(T_{PV} - T_{STC}), \quad (2)$$

where β is the sensitivity of the PV efficiency to temperature changes ($-0.005 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), T_{STC} is the temperature at standard testing conditions ($25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and T_{PV} is the PV cell temperature following Tamizhmani et al. (2003):

$$T_{PV} = 0.943T_{air} + 0.028G - 1.528U_{10} + 4.3, \quad (3)$$

where T_{air} is the 2 meter temperature and U_{10} the 10 meter wind speed.

For the soiling loss S we use the Kimber et al. (2006) soiling model, with a soiling loss rate of $6.25 \cdot 10^{-5}$ per day and a precipitation threshold of 6 mm. Once the 24-hour accumulated precipitation exceeds this threshold, panels are assumed clean ($S = 0$) and do not experience soiling for the next 14 days as the soil is still considered damp. We do not account for manual cleaning.

2.3 Identifying warm & dry spells

To show the impact of extreme weather situations on PV energy production, we identify warm and dry spells using the hourly simulation data of 2 meter temperature and precipitation. Days

are considered dry if the 24 hour accumulated precipitation, starting from 0 UTC, is less than 1 mm. Days are considered warm if the daily maximum temperature exceeds the 5-day running 90th percentile of the daily maximum temperature of the corresponding day of the year between 2021 and 2049 (Brunner, 2025). We then define warm and dry spells as all periods of three or more days that are classified as both warm and dry.

3 Solar energy atlas

3.1 Global PV potential: mean, variability, and trend

Figure 1: Global maps of the mean annual solar photovoltaics (PV) potential energy production between 2021 and 2049, based on the Cycle 4 IFS (top) and ICON (bottom) simulations. Annual mean capacity factors have been multiplied by 24 (hours per day) and 365 (days per year) to obtain the potential energy production in kWh per installed kW peak (kWp).

Figure 1 shows the mean annual PV potential for the IFS and ICON simulations, averaged between 2021 and 2049. Both simulations show similar global patterns, with relatively high PV potentials in (sub-)tropical and mountainous regions that decrease towards higher latitudes due

Figure 2: Global maps of the inter-annual standard deviation of the PV potential between 2021 and 2049, based on the Cycle 4 IFS (top) and ICON (bottom) simulations. Annual mean capacity factors have been multiplied by 24 (hours per day) and 365 (days per year) to obtain the potential energy production in kWh per installed kW peak (kWp).

to the lower yearly averaged incoming solar radiation. However, the PV potentials are generally higher in ICON than in IFS, up to about 50% in some regions (e.g. the northern part of South America, and Southeast Asia). The higher PV potentials in ICON are largely the result of higher surface solar irradiances (e.g. see deliverable D9.3). However, in some regions (e.g. the Sahel) we find that differences in PV potential can also be attributed to large differences in soiling losses (not shown), likely reflecting different large-scale precipitation patterns.

The standard deviation of the annual PV potential, as a measure of the interannual variability, is shown in Figure 2. In both simulations, the interannual PV potential variability largely reflects arid regions that have large fluctuations in yearly precipitation frequency and amount, resulting in large differences in soiling losses between years. However, the large PV variability in ICON at the east coast of North America and in northern Asia is mostly the result of the strong trend in these regions (Figure 3).

These large decadal trends in PV potential in ICON, which we consider very unlikely, are mostly the result of increasing surface solar irradiances: even without accounting for soiling losses this

Figure 3: Global maps of the decadal trend in PV potential between 2021 and 2049, based on the Cycle 4 IFS (top) and ICON (bottom) simulations. Annual mean capacity factors have been multiplied by 24 (hours per day) and 365 (days per year) to obtain the potential energy production in kWh per installed kW peak (kWp).

increasing trend is still present with similar magnitudes (Veerman, 2025). In ICON, these regions (eastern North America, northern Asia) dry out strongly in summer, with June-July-August (JJA) averaged soil moisture contents, precipitation rates and liquid cloud amounts all exhibiting a strong negative decadal trend. However, as these large trends are unrealistic, we should also consider the mean PV potential and variability thereof unreliable in these regions.

Outside of these regions, the PV potential trends in IFS and ICON generally also show quite different patterns, partly due to different trends in surface solar irradiance and partly due to differences in precipitation affecting the soiling losses. In the Amazon region, both simulations show a comparable increase in PV potential which is driven by an increase in surface solar irradiance and consistent with future projections shown in literature (e.g. Feron et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2024).

More results, such as maps of PV potential without accounting for soiling losses or more detailed maps zoomed in on specific regions (e.g. Figure 4), as well as monthly-mean global data of the PV capacity factors, are available on Zenodo (Veerman, 2025).

Figure 4: Maps, zoomed in on western Europe, of the mean solar photovoltaics potential energy production between 2021 and 2049 (top) and decadal trend thereof (bottom), based on the Cycle 4 IFS (left) and ICON (right) simulations. Mean capacity factors have been multiplied by 24 (hours per day) and 365 (days per year) to obtain the (trend in) potential energy production in kWh per installed kW peak (kWp)

3.2 PV potential during warm & dry spells

Figure 5 shows the impact of warm & dry spells (see section 2.3) on the mean PV potential. The effect of warm and dry atmospheric conditions is twofold: on the one hand, these conditions are generally associated with lower cloud coverages and thus higher surface solar irradiances, leading to a higher PV potential. On the other hand, higher temperatures reduce the efficiency of PV panels and drier conditions result in higher soiling losses, leading to lower PV potentials. In tropical, maritime, and continental climates, the PV potential is generally higher during warm & dry spell days, indicating that the first pathway (higher solar irradiance) dominates. In arid regions, PV potential are slightly lower during warm & dry spells, showing that second pathway (lower efficiency and more soiling) dominates, presumably because in these regions cloud coverages are also very low on days that are not counted as warm & dry spell.

Figure 5: Global maps of the difference in mean PV potential based on days classified as ≥ 3 day warm & dry spell and the mean PV potential based on days not classified as a ≥ 3 day warm & dry spell, based on the Cycle 4 IFS (top) and ICON (bottom) simulation between 2021 and 2049. Days either within or outside of warm & dry spells are grouped and averaged per day of year over the 29 year time period. Annual PV potentials are then computed by averaging all days of year with at least one warm & dry spell event. Mean capacity factors have been multiplied by 24 (hours per day) and 365 (days per year) to obtain the potential energy production in kWh per installed kW peak (kWp).

4 Model evaluation

The evaluation of the simulations presented in this section has been performed by Iberdrola to assess their relevance and potential applications for the renewable energy industry. The evaluation focuses on global horizontal irradiance (GHI) and energy production estimates for PV plants. Figure 6 shows an evaluation of the monthly mean GHI in IFS and ICON at three meteorological masts equipped with GHI sensors located in Mexico, Brazil and Spain

Differences between the observations and simulations vary per location, with no clear driver to account for these deviations. Results in Spain for IFS and ICON show good agreement with

Figure 6: Time series of monthly irradiation in the cycle 4 ICON and IFS simulations at three meteorological masts with global horizontal irradiance sensors located in Spain (top), Mexico (middle), and Brazil (bottom).

measurements between 2021 and 2024, although ICON tends to overestimate GHI in summer. Annual mean errors vary per year, but both models show good agreement to observations. Averaged over the entire period, the relative mean bias error (rMBE) of ICON is 2.8% and the rMBE of IFS is -0.9%. Consequently, both models may be suitable candidates for energy resource estimation in PV plant design. In Mexico (2020-2023), ICON overestimates GHI in summer and early autumn. IFS underestimates GHI in late spring and early summer, and overestimates GHI in late summer. The average rMBE is +5% for ICON and only -1% for IFS. However, both simulations have large inter-annual variability in rMBE, which generates large uncertainty in the results. In Brazil (2020-2024), the validation shows that both simulations tend to underestimate GHI, especially in winter and early spring (Jan-Apr). The average yearly rMBE is -5.5% for ICON and -10.3% for IFS, with strong variations in rMBE between years.

Additionally, a validation of energy production estimates at three PV plant operated by Iberdrola was performed (Figure 7). The PV plant model used for design (using commercial software PVSyst) is applied to GHI and temperature data from either observations or simulations, giving a

Figure 7: Mean percentage error of the annual PV energy production estimated with PVsyst based on ICON and IFS relative to the annual PV energy production based on observations. The evaluation periods are 2021-2023, 2022-2023, and 2022-2024 for the three PV plants, respectively.

fair comparison of energy assessment results for the three plants. To anonymize the data, plants are named 1, 2, and 3, located in southern, central and northeast Spain respectively. ICON strongly overestimates the energy production in all three locations by 10% to 20%, whereas errors of IFS are well below 10% (2.9%, 5.6%, and 8.8% in location 1, 2, and 3, respectively). The overestimated energy production is largely the result of an overestimated solar irradiance, combined with underestimated surface temperatures resulting in more efficient PV panels.

Despite the results in Spain showing that IFS has better agreement with observations than ICON, no general trend can be derived from this comparison. As shown in the previous GHI analysis, model data have a strong local dependency and therefore both models should be tested and validated in every location to identify the one that better fits observations.

5 Conclusion

We developed a solar energy atlas using the cycle 4 simulations of ICON and IFS, which is fully available online (Veerman, 2025). The solar energy atlas includes global maps of the mean annual PV energy production potential between 2021-2049, the inter-annual variability of the PV potential, and decadal trends thereof. We also show the impact of multi-day warm & dry spells on the mean PV potential. Last, we present an evaluation of the simulations in terms of global horizontal irradiance and PV energy production.

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